

European network to promote grazing and to support grazing-based farms on their economic and ecologic performances as well as on animal welfare

Project Acronym: Grazing4AgroEcology

Project Number: 101059626

Deliverable No.: D2.3

Deliverable Title: 120 practice abstracts (including videos) in EIP-Agri-format describing one practice per farm promoting AE

Responsible Partner: Bioland-ST

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Programme	Contract Number	Duration	Start
Horizon Europe	101059626	42 Months	September 2022

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1 Introduction

Task 2.3 Creation of an inventory of farmer best practices to optimise production, economic, ecological, cultural and societal values (M2-M20)

Task lead: Bioland-Südtirol in collaboration with all partners

The objective of Task 2.3 is to create an inventory of best practices to optimise farm performance in the areas of economics, ecology, culture and societal value of the farm as well as on animal welfare.

The partner farms (PFs) in each national network, with the national facilitator agents (FAs), identified practices used on their farm to promote grazing for agroecology. A description of the implementation of the practice on that farm and the benefits perceived by the farmer were developed under the guidance of the FA. Every eight member state translates the co-design approach into practice with their respective partner farm network consisting of 15 farms each. Thus, 15 innovation videos and 15 practice abstracts per member state were created, resulting into a total of 120 videos and 120 practice abstracts. The innovation videos (0.5-2 minutes) consisted of farmers explaining and demonstrating a best agroecological practice to complement each practice abstract using the media training provided in T 5.4. Each practice abstract and innovation video presents a specific best practice which can be classified to one or multiple pillars of AE (animal welfare, reducing pollution, enhancing diversity, biodiversity, reducing inputs).

2 Methodology

In the individual partner countries, participating partner farms implementing innovative grazing practices were visited and the innovative practice surveyed by means of the first-visit questionnaire (T2.1) and recorded in a video (T2.3). The following templates were created to provide a framework for the creation of the videos and abstracts.

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Template for practice abstracts (part of D2.3 120 Practice abstracts in EIP-Agri format (incl. videos) describing one practice per farm promoting AE)

Contents of D2.3:

- 120 short practice videos (0.5-2 minutes) (one per partner farm)
- 120 practice abstracts in EIP-format describing one practice per farm promoting grazing for Agroecology (one per partner farm)

Involved actors: Facilitator Agent (FA), Partner Farm Network (PF)

Definition: a practice abstract is a short (1000-1500 characters, word count – no spaces) summary for practitioners in the native language of the Partner Farm and in English on the (final or expected) outcomes.

This summary should be as interesting as possible for farmers/end-users, using a direct and easily understandable language and pointing out entrepreneurial elements which are particularly relevant for practitioners (e.g. related to cost, productivity etc.). Research oriented aspects which do not help the understanding of the practice itself should be avoided.

Source: <https://ec.europa.eu/eip/agriculture/en/content/eip-agri-common-format>

Format: it is strictly defined by the Commission.
The practice abstract consists of:

1. Short and easily understandable title (one key sentence, max 150 char.)
2. Short summaries in easily understandable language (max 1500 char.)
 - a. What problem will the knowledge generated solve for the end-user?
 - b. What will be the main benefits to the practitioner?
 - c. Main outcome/recommendation (2-3 main results)

Contents: to describe the innovative practice, the following elements should be addressed:

- Relevant economic, social, environmental, technological, legal and political themes to be considered for the implementation of the innovation at the own farm.
- Background of the innovation: What was the context? What was the problem to solve? What were farmers' motivations?
- Detailed description of the innovation: What did the farmer do?
- Results obtained from the innovation: What has been improved (workload, profitability, higher production, etc.,) and to what extent?
- Adoption criteria of the innovation: In which context and at which condition the innovation can be adopted by other farmers?
- Future prospects of the innovation development from the farmer point of view: What can still be improved? How can it be disseminated? What are the threats?

Workflow for submitting the practice abstracts: the practice abstracts should be sent, linked to the complementary video, to Bioland Südtirol (G4AE@bioland-suedtirol.it), in order to guarantee an updated overview of the progress of Task 2.3. They will be then transferred to Teagasc and GLZ for the publication on the EIP-AGRI webpage. All abstracts must be delivered **at the latest by March 2024**.

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Fig. 1: Template and guidelines for the creation of practice abstracts

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Template for videos complementary to practice abstracts

(part of D2.3 120 Practice abstracts in EIP-Agri format (incl. videos) describing one practice per farm promoting AE)

Involved actors: Facilitator Agent (FA), Partner Farm Network (PF)

Deliverable, D2.3:

- 120 short practice videos (0.5-2 minutes) (one per farm)
- 120 practice abstracts in EIP-format describing one practice per farm promoting grazing for Agroecology (one per farm) – complementary to video

A short practice video is a short (0.5 – 2 minutes) video shot in landscape format of the farmer explaining and demonstrating the innovative practice supporting one of the 5 G4AE pillars on their farm. The practice video is complementary to the practice abstract. The video can be recorded in native languages with subtitles translating to English available for the YouTube channel and website.

The video should at least contain the following information:

- Farmer introduction
- Introduction to his/her farm
- Name of the innovative practice taking place on farm
- When implementation of the innovation began on farm
- Why the innovation was implemented/motivation for implementation
- Main results/outcomes for the farmer from the innovation
- A reference to the practical recommendations through a link to practice abstracts

The video should be as interesting as possible for farmers/end users, using direct and easily understood language and point out the main elements, which are particularly relevant and beneficial to farmer. Research orientated aspects which do not help understanding of the practice itself should be avoided.

The video format should:

- Be shot in landscape
- Contain 5 shots for action (best practice outlined below)

Intro& outro:
Example attached in email.

Sound in video:

- No background music to the videos
- Farmer talking only if possible
- Only natural farming sounds (animals grazing, birds, wind, etc.,)

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Fig. 2: Template and guidelines for the creation of innovation videos complementing each practice abstract

Translations:

- English translation of the video must be included in white legible font (ivy style sans) at the bottom of the video

Workflow for submitting the practice abstracts: the video abstracts should be sent, with the linked practice abstract & farmer consent form, to Martin Unterweger in Bioland Südtirol (G4AE@bioland-suedtirol.it), in order to guarantee an updated overview of the progress of Task 2.3.

They will be then transferred to Teagasc and GLZ for the publication on the EIP-AGRI webpage.

Delivering plan for the videos: All videos have to be delivered **at the latest by February 2024**.

Farmer consent form: Included in email

Important: All videos must be recorded in the grazing season 2023, if grazing during the wintertime is not possible.

Best practice for taking videos – FA training

Below information adapted from facilitator agent training in Lisbon (21st March 2023) with Matthias Shuhn.

- Best camera angle for talking head style video (farmer speaking – most common) is eye level
- Microphone should be used and should be as close to farmers mouth as possible
- To keep farmer at ease try film them in their natural situations
- Natural light
- Take as much footage as possible & cut it down after using VN software
- Tripod can help keep the footage steady
- Plan what you want to film on farm ahead of time
 - Choose a innovative practice
 - Have an idea of the footage you want to take
 - Be transparent with the farmer and create a comfortable environment
 - If possible, send farmer a list of questions you would like answered & give a time frame for farmer to answer those questions

Shot selection:

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5 shots for action:

1. What?
 - a. 10 second detail shot
 - b. For example, film the farmers hands while doing a task related to the innovation
2. Who?
 - a. Close up of farmer
3. Where?
 - a. Establishment shot
4. Over the shoulder shot
 - a. Similar size shot to a close up
5. Ending
 - a. Make sure to film an end
 - b. Get a close up of the farmers face

- Each shot for action should have at least 10 seconds of footage that can be edited
- Have several actions in each video

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The shared logo shows a stylized green field with a blue sky and a white sun. The text 'Funded by the European Union' is written in a small font below the logo.

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Based on the FA-video training during the 2nd GPA-Meeting in Lisbon on 20 March 2023, all partners began filming the first videos and writing the corresponding abstract following the templates. Both the videos and the abstracts have been reviewed by Bioland Südtirol and

Teagasc. The project partners then incorporated the technical and formal corrections and made the materials available again on the project`s sharepoint on MS Teams.

At the GPA meeting on 23 September 2023 in Rennes, it was decided by a mentimeter poll (Fig. 1) that a uniform intro and a uniform outro (only logo lettering) should be added by the individual project partners before submission. The individual start and end images still make each video unique because they are kept country-specific.

Fig. 3: Mentimeter poll results from the GPA-Meeting in Rennes

Figures 2 and 3 show the example for the intro and the outro lettering decided in Rennes.

Intro lettering:

Fig. 4: Intro example for each innovation video

Outro lettering:

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Farmer: Marko Hekert

Facilitator agent: Siw Fasting

Video producer: Franziska Schmidt

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Website: www.grazing4agroecology.eu
f: <https://www.facebook.com/Grazing4AgroEcology/>
t: https://twitter.com/NEurope_G4AE
in: <https://www.linkedin.com/company/89048577/admin/>
e: <https://www.youtube.com/@Grazing4AgroEcology>

Fig. 5: Outro example for each innovation video

3 Results

120 practice abstracts and 120 videos promoting agroecology are available on the project's Sharepoint. Each practice abstract and innovation video present a specific best practice which can be classified to one or multiple pillars (animal welfare, reducing pollution, enhancing diversity, biodiversity, reducing inputs). They will be available to the public on the project's homepage upon formalizing consent regulations.

Practice abstracts:

<https://grazing4agroecology.eu/innovations/innovations-practise-abstracts/>

Innovation videos:

<https://grazing4agroecology.eu/innovations/infothek-video/>

Consortium:

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